

NON-SPECIFIC PROTECTION FACTORS AND THE CYTOKINE SYSTEM IN POSTOPERATIVE VENTRAL HERNIAS

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Abstract: Incisional ventral hernias (POVH) account for up to 20-22% of all external abdominal hernias and are second in frequency after inguinal ones. Over 5% of all laparotomies are complicated by the formation of postoperative ventral hernias [4,5]. A fundamentally important condition for the successful treatment of patients with postoperative ventral hernias is the need to assess immunological reactivity both before surgery and in the postoperative period. [1,2,3]

Keywords: postoperative ventral hernias, superoxide dismutase.

The aim of the study was to study acute phase proteins and levels of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines in patients with incisional ventral hernias.

Materials and methods of research: In the period 2021-2022, a prospective study was performed in 80 patients with postoperative ventral hernias. The study included 15 men (18.8%) with an average age of 56 ± 2.46 years and 65 women (81.2%) with an average age of 60 ± 1.32 years. The control group consisted of 30 healthy volunteers. The inclusion criteria for this group was the presence of a postoperative ventral hernia in a patient who agreed to an immunological examination and planned surgical treatment in TashPMI clinics using a polypropylene mesh implant from Lintex, Esfil standard and Esfil easy (Russia, St. Petersburg). Immunological studies were carried out by determining the level of serum cytokines (IL-1 β , TNF- α , and IL-4), C-reactive protein and lactoferrin by ELISA (Cytokin, St. Petersburg).

Results and conclusions of the study: The conducted studies showed how the initial immune status changes: the content of all studied pro-inflammatory cytokines and the level of IL-4 increase. Thus, the concentration of IL-1 β increases by 4.6, TNF- α by 7, and IL-4 by 3.6 times. Perhaps a more significant increase in the level of TNF- α is associated with its more pronounced systemic effect. It is known that CRP, interacting with T-lymphocytes, phagocytes and platelets, regulates their functions during inflammation. The level of C-reactive protein in patients with postoperative ventral hernias is 1.6 times higher than the control values ($p < 0.01$), and the level of lactoferrin, one of the indicators of innate immunity and which is also an acute phase protein, is reduced (420.2 ± 27.3 ng/ml) compared with the values of the control group (536.2 ± 32.4 ng/ml) i.e. 1.27 times.

Thus, the development of POVH is accompanied by an increase in the level of both pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines, as well as a multidirectional value of acute phase proteins, i.e. indicate an imbalance between Th1 and Th2 types of immune response.

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